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COVID-19 vaccines vs. new SARS-CoV-2 strains

Domina Petric, MD

SARS-CoV-2 is an enveloped virus with a single-stranded positive sense RNA genome. Vaccine efficacy can be limited by mutations in RNA viruses. Most mutations in the SARS-CoV-2 genome have no impact on viral function, but certain variants have garnered widespread attention because of their rapid emergence within populations and potential for transmission or clinical implications.

SARS-CoV-2 is an enveloped virus with a single-stranded positive sense RNA genome. Vaccine efficacy can be limited by mutations in RNA viruses, as observed for the influenza virus as a representative pathogenic virus¹⁻³.

Like other viruses, SARS-CoV-2 evolves over time. Most mutations in the SARS-CoV-2 genome have no impact on viral function. Certain variants have garnered widespread attention because of their rapid emergence within populations and potential for transmission or clinical implications:

1. **B.1.1.7 lineage** – This variant, also known as variant of concern (VOC) 202012/01, was first identified in the United Kingdom in late 2020 and was temporally associated with an increase in regional infections. This variant contains more than a dozen mutations compared with

other circulating strains, with several within the spike protein. It has subsequently been identified in other countries, including the United States.

2. **B.1.351 lineage** – This variant, also known as 501Y.V2, was identified in South Africa in late 2020. It is phylogenetically distinct from B.1.1.7 but shares several mutations, including the spike protein mutation N501Y. Surveillance data in South Africa indicate that this variant rapidly became the dominant strain, suggesting that it also has the potential for increased transmissibility.
3. **G614 polymorphism** – A study that monitored amino acid changes in the spike protein of SARS-CoV-2 included in a large sequence database identified a D614G

(glycine for aspartic acid) substitution that became the dominant polymorphism globally over time. In vitro, pseudotyped viruses harboring the G614 variant resulted in higher viral titers than those with the D614 variant. Engineering the G614 variant into an infectious clone also resulted in higher levels of infectious virus in a human epithelial lung tissue culture system as well as higher upper respiratory tract viral titers in a hamster infection model⁴.

4. **B.1.1.28 lineage** has been evolving in Brazil since February 2020, but the recent emergence of sub-lineages with convergent mutations in the spike (S) protein raises concern about the potential impact on viral infectivity and immune escape. The lineage P.1 (alias of B.1.1.28.1) is an emerging variant that harbors several amino acid mutations including S:K417T, S:E484K, and S:N501Y⁵.

The variant known as P.1 or VOC202101/02 in the UK was first detected in travelers from Brazil who arrived in Japan in January 2021. It involves 17 unique amino acid changes, three deletions, four synonymous mutations, and one 4nt insertion. It has

several mutations that are known to be biologically important, including E484K and N501Y. The N501Y mutation, which is also a feature of the English variant, has been linked to increased infectivity and virulence in mouse models. The E484K mutation is thought to be associated with escape from the neutralizing antibodies produced by the body against SARS-CoV-2. This mutation is present in the South African variant as well⁶.

Delaying the second dose of COVID-19 vaccines has some experts concerned including Ramón Lorenzo-Redondo, a virologist at Northwestern University Feinberg School of Medicine in Chicago, particularly without a lot of evidence suggesting how well one dose works. For the COVID-19 vaccine, if people's second doses are delayed long enough, it is possible that low numbers of neutralizing antibodies triggered by only one dose may only partially fight an infection. That might provide more time for variants of the virus with immune-dodging mutations to arise and thrive and be transmitted to other people. If immune-dodging variants do arise as a result of shot delays and spread to lots of people that could deal a blow to vaccines' effectiveness. If mutations arose that prevented vaccine-induced antibodies from binding to the virus, or caused antibodies to bind less tightly, that virus

variant may be more likely to infect cells than variants without the mutation and thus cause disease⁷.

Two days after the Los Angeles Public Health Department announced that the much-talked-about UK variant of Covid-19, known as B.1.1.7, had been identified in the region, the California Department of Public Health revealed that another lesser-known strain had been circulating in the county as well. Known as **L452R**, the newly announced arrival was first identified in Denmark in March. It showed up in California as early as May. Dr. Charles Chiu, a virologist and professor of laboratory medicine at UCSF who, in concert with state authorities, has been genetically sequencing test samples to identify new variants said early indications are the L452R might be less susceptible to the currently approved vaccines, but more investigation is needed⁸.

CONCLUSION

Two important questions need to be answered regarding the COVID-19 vaccines and new SARS-CoV-2 strains:

1. Will vaccines be effective against new strains?
2. Will vaccines actually trigger SARS-CoV-2 mutations and the emergence of new strains⁹?

REFERENCES

1. Zhu N, Zhang D, Wang W, et al. A novel coronavirus from patients with pneumonia in China, 2019. *N. Engl. J. Med.* 2020;382:727-733.
2. Barcik W, Boutin RCT, Sokolowska M, Finlay BB. The role of lung and gut microbiota in the pathology of asthma. *Immunity* 2020;52:241-255.
3. Chehrazi N, Cipriano LE, Enns EA. Dynamics of drug resistance: optimal control of an infectious disease. *Oper. Res.* 2019;67:619-650.
4. McIntosh K. Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19): Epidemiology, virology, and prevention. Hirsch MS, Bloom A, ed. UpToDate. Waltham, MA: UpToDate Inc. <https://www.uptodate.com> (Accessed on January 19, 2021.)
5. Naveca F, da Costa C, Nascimento V, et al. SARS-CoV-2 reinfection by the new Variant of Concern (VOC) P.1 in Amazonas, Brazil. Jan 18, 2021. Retrieved from <https://virological.org/t/sars-cov-2-reinfection-by-the-new-variant-of->

concern-voc-p-1-in-amazonas-brazil/596
(cited on Jan 19, 2021)

6. Mahase E. Covid-19: What new variants are emerging and how are they being investigated? *BMJ* 2021;372:n158
7. de Jesus EG. Could delaying a second vaccine dose lead to more dangerous coronavirus strains? Jan 14, 2021. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencenews.org/article/coronavirus-covid-19-vaccine-delay-second-dose-dangerous-strains> (Jan 19, 2021)
8. Tapp T. Another New Covid-19 Variant Discovered in L.A. Might be Vaccine Resistant, Researcher Says; Strain First Identified in Denmark. Jan 18, 2021. Retrieved from <https://deadline.com/2021/01/another-new-covid-19-variant-in-l-a-vaccine-resistant-denmark-1234675834/> (cited on Jan 19, 2021)
9. Vranes J. EVOLUCIJA NOVOG KORONA VIRUSA -JOŠ INFEKTIVNIJE NOVE VARIJANTE. Jan 2021. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348357099_EVOLUCIJA_NOVOG_KORONA_VIRUSA_-JOS_INFEKTIVNIJE_NOVE_VARIJANTE (cited on Jan 19, 2021)